

Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities

D6.1

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Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities

DELIVERABLE TYPE

R – Document, report

MONTH AND DATE OF DELIVERY

M6, February 2023

WORK PACKAGE

WP 6

LEADER

LOBA

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU – Public

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DOI/ISBN

10.5281/zenodo.7682336

Programme	Contract Number	Duration	Start
Horizon Europe	101060537	36 Months	September 2022

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Revision History

Version	Date	Reviewer	Modifications
0.1	22/02/2023	Alexandros Koukovinis, Joana Oliveira (LOBA)	First draft
0.2	24/02/2023	Claudia Iasillo, Alessio Livio Spera (APRE), Alexandre Almeida, Candela Bravo (LOBA)	Comments from partners
1.0	27/02/2023	Alexandros Koukovinis (LOBA), Alessio Livio Spera (APRE)	Final Version

The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf.

Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
BG	Background
CA	Consortium Agreement
EC	European Commission
EPC	European Patent Convention
ER	Exploitable Results
EM	Exploitation Manager
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
FG	Foreground
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
TBD	To be determined
WIPO	World Intellectual Property Organisation
WP	Work Package
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement

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1 Executive Summary

The objective of this deliverable is to provide a detailed overview of the dissemination, communication, and exploitation strategy that will be implemented during the BlueRev project. This strategy is integrated under WP6 Dissemination & Communication, exploitation and replication.

As WP6 leader, LOBA will be responsible for the overall management and support of activities defined under the present dissemination and communication plan, including monitoring the performance and developing the main dissemination and communication channels, tools and materials to be used during the project. In collaboration with Task 6.5, led by APRE (Exploitation manager), the present plan will also address the exploitation and sustainability strategy, aiming at ensuring the timely promotion of the project's outcomes and engagement of parties outside the Consortium, interested in using or adopting them.

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan outlines a detailed planning of the dissemination and communication activities systematically, intending to perform actions and campaigns that reach specific groups and audiences for specific purposes. The first version of the exploitation and sustainability plan included in this document, provides the strategy, methodology, and tools to be implemented during the project to pave the way for the exploitation of its results.

The current version of the exploitation and sustainability plan also includes an overview of BlueRev's Background and Foreground Intellectual Property and a preliminary screening of the project's key exploitable results along with potential pathways for their exploitation (as identified by all partners using a dedicated tool, we dubbed as the IPR Matrix) as well as an individual exploitation plan per partner. The exploitable results of the project as well as the provisions pertaining to their exploitation will be updated during the project to deliver the "Final Exploitation and replication plan" (D6.5) in M36.

All partners will be actively involved in the dissemination, exploitation and communication actions implementation, and their involvement will contribute to satisfactory dissemination of the project's objectives, activities, and results. In general, the expected contribution from partners is to:

- Implement publicity and dissemination campaigns in their own countries and at European level;
- Exploit their contacts and networks;
- Supply news and updates for the website and newsletter;
- Help to keep the project's Social Media Accounts (SMAs) alive and active;
- Participate in relevant events to promote the project and its outcomes;
- Contribute with scientific papers acknowledging the BlueRev project.

2 Introduction

This deliverable provides detailed information about the strategies, methodologies, channels, materials, and tools used to support an effective dissemination, exploitation and communication of the project. Further updates of this document will be provided in the periodic reports and on M19 under D6.3 and on M36 under D6.5 Final exploitation strategy.

This deliverable is divided into 10 main sections:

- Section 4 “Dissemination and communication strategy” presents the approach and objectives.
- Section 5 “Target groups” including drivers and the benefits from the project.
- Section 6 “Partners support in the D&C” provides guidelines on how partners can contribute to D&C.
- Section 7 “Project identity” including the logo and additional material.
- Section 8 “Channels and tools” presents the different channels and tools to be used for disseminating and communicating project activities and outcomes, including the project website, social media accounts, YouTube Channel, newsletter, and media coverage.
- Section 9 “Events” describes the different types of events where the project will be communicated and disseminated.
- Section 10 “Joint D&C with other projects and initiatives” describes the collaborations to be established.
- Section 11 “Reporting procedure” provides instructions for the partners to report the D&C activities and the KPIs.
- Sections 12 & 13 “Time plan” and conclusions provide the schedule for the next actions and the conclusions.
- Section 14 “Exploitation and Sustainability Plan” details the methodology to be implemented during the project including the Intellectual Property management, the identification of Background, Foreground, and project’s key exploitable assets, the tools to identify all aforementioned assets, and also exploitation plans per key project result as well as per individual partner of the BlueRev consortium. This first version of the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan will also identify the relevant target beneficiaries of the project which are the initially identified target groups that may be further enriched in the context of the forthcoming Exploitation and Sustainability update.

3 BlueRev in a nutshell

BlueRev project focuses on the revitalization of European local communities through innovative bio-based business models, governance frameworks, and social innovations in the blue bio-based sector, to underline the benefits the wide deployment of the bio-based sector can offer.

To achieve its main objective, BlueRev project will identify and define a range of systems in the blue bio-based sector in 3 different pilot regions throughout Europe (i.e., Denmark, Italy, and Estonia) to tailor value chains, from valorisation of co-products as feedstock to processing/conversion to final products, in order to revitalise local communities, both in a territorial and social sense and contribute to positive environmental and social impacts.

The project will first analyse these value chains according to social, economic and environmental barriers and potentialities, business models, local capacities (e.g., feedstocks, infrastructure, human skills, etc.) and innovation actors, including community knowledge and marginalised groups, by using existing or defining improved monitoring system and indicators to evaluate the effectiveness of the value chains. The project will also analyse the existing governance framework and how it can be improved.

The analysis will serve BlueRev to develop or replicate new governance and business models allowing the transition towards socially and environmentally responsible behaviour within all ranges (e.g. regulatory measures, corporate responsibility initiatives, education), to enable sufficient impacts and performances of the specific value chains and to allow replication across Europe.

In doing that BlueRev will ensure an efficient engagement of all actors, including local and regional authorities, primary biomass producers, SMEs, civil society organisations including NGOs, higher education organizations (e.g. universities including blue bioeconomy graduate courses), community knowledge and marginalised groups via robust and transparent communication and awareness-raising campaigns (Figure 1).

Figure 1: BlueRev concept

4 Dissemination and communication Strategy

As the leader of Work Package 6, LOBA is responsible for the communication and dissemination of the project's objectives, activities, and outcomes. The dissemination and communication of the project will respond to the needs of the project according to its progress, in this sense we distinguish the following three main stages:

- 1st stage: establish the conditions for successful dissemination and communication (plan, identity, tools, channels);
- 2nd stage: maintain continuous and steady dissemination and communication – create and increase awareness;
- 3rd stage: intensify the dissemination and communication towards the project's sustainability and exploitation.

The main objectives of this Dissemination and Communication Plan are to:

- Raise awareness of the project's activities and events;
- Engage relevant target groups and stakeholders to get involved in the project's activities that will be implemented around the main action pillars of the project:
 - Analysis of social innovation processes
 - Analysis of business models
 - Analysis of governance models
 - Environmental Assessment
 - Communication and Dissemination
 - Replication throughout Europe
 - Engagement of stakeholders in the co-creation of new solutions
 - Case Studies demonstrations
 - Training and Coaching programmes
- Communicate and disseminate the results of the project among the main target groups;
- Make use of a variety of channels to efficiently communicate the project amongst the main target groups;
- Develop printed support materials (such as posters, roll-ups, stationary, etc.) and digital materials (videos, infographics, etc.) when necessary, but also be environmentally conscious in the production of printed materials;
- Create a link to other existing projects that deal with Entrepreneurship, Business, Education and Policy in the Blue Economy (in connection with T2.1);
- Ensure regular communication to keep the target groups, the media and other projects/initiatives updated on the project, through emailing, press releases and newsletters.

The dissemination and communication strategy outlined in this document will be reviewed and updated for the respective reporting periods and under deliverable D6.2 Updated plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities, due in Month 18. As for the Exploitation and replication plan, some initial guidelines for its formulation have been included in this deliverable but it is expected to be developed further in month 18 as well, under D6.2, and finalized in month 36 under deliverable D6.3 “Final Exploitation and replication plan”.

For the successful implementation of the Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities, the WP leader will be following a plan divided in three steps:

1. Knowledge: defining a coherent and consistent campaign strategically aligned with BlueRev scope and objectives;
2. Strategy: creating a holistic dimension that will position BlueRev brand, values and attributes;
3. Action plan: detailed planning of communication activities considering a broader approach, but also targeted campaigns to specific groups and audiences.

In addition, a defined timeline has been set to implement the plan:

1. Planning of Activities (M1 – M6): Identify the communication and dissemination strategy and plan to ensure the best impact of BlueRev activities and outcomes. Linked with the deliverable D6.1 “Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities”.
2. Implementation Phase (M1 – M36): Produce a comprehensive set of tools (supports and channels) to diffuse key messages extracted from BlueRev activities to stakeholders in a way that encourages stakeholders to be connected with the project.
3. Monitoring Activities (M1 – M36): Carefully monitor and assess the impact and performance of dissemination activities against pre-established key performance indicators (KPI’s). Linked with the deliverables D6.2 “Report on communication activities” [M19], and D6.4 “Report on communication activities” [M36].
4. Exploitation and Sustainability (M1 – M36): Identify and establish the mechanisms needed to ensure persistent and long-lasting visibility and exploitation of BlueRev outcomes, linked with the Deliverable “Final Exploitation and replication plan”, due at M36 (D6.3).

4.1 Objectives of the Dissemination and communication plan

The objectives of the BlueRev dissemination and communication are two-fold.

On one hand, to establish an appropriate strategy on how to reach and engage with relevant target groups for specific purposes, through a multi-channel approach and engaging set of tools and actions.

On the other hand, to offer partners a set of guidelines, responsibilities, and timelines on how, when and where to disseminate the project, as well as to encourage them to use their channels (corporate websites, social networks, etc.) to support the communication project and dissemination of its results.

Ultimately, the dissemination and communication plan aims to contribute to establishing the ideal conditions to:

- Raise awareness of the project's activities and events;
- Communicate and disseminate the findings and results of BlueRev to relevant target groups;
- Identify and use the right channels to efficiently communicate with the target groups and stakeholders (including the identification of events, social media networks, press coverage, multiplier organisations, etc.);
- Produce the necessary supporting materials to ensure effective dissemination, including printed material (i.e., brochure, poster, roll-up, goodies, etc.) and digital material (videos, factsheets, infographics, etc.);
- Contribute to the collaboration with other existing projects relevant to BlueRev and mutual dissemination (supporting task 2.1);
- Facilitate regular communication, through press releases and newsletters, to inform about the latest news and developments of the project to the media.

5 Target groups and the benefits from BlueRev

Within BlueRev lie the interests and benefits of several target groups, as can be seen below:

- **National, regional, local authorities and regional clusters:** Enhanced knowledge of blue economy concepts and sustainable practices, access to new technologies and data to support policy and decision-making, and opportunities for collaboration and networking with other regional clusters.
- **Primary biomass producers, associations, and cooperatives:** Increased knowledge of sustainable and circular economy practices, access to new technologies and tools to improve efficiency and reduce waste, and opportunities for collaboration with other producers, associations, and cooperatives.
- **Organisations and SMEs:** Improved access to finance and funding opportunities, increased knowledge of sustainable and circular economy practices, opportunities for collaboration and networking with other organisations and SMEs, and potential to gain a competitive advantage through adoption of sustainable practices.
- **Civil society organisations including NGOs:** Improved knowledge of blue economy concepts and sustainable practices, opportunities for collaboration with other organisations and civil society groups, and potential to influence policy and decision-making through engagement with the project.
- **Knowledge providers:** Access to new data and technologies to support research and education, opportunities for collaboration with other knowledge providers and research institutions, and potential to contribute to the development of best practices in blue economy research and education.
- **Community knowledge:** Increased knowledge and awareness of sustainable and circular economy practices, the potential to participate in project design and implementation, and opportunities for collaboration with other community groups.
- **Scientific communities:** Access to new data and technologies to support research and education, opportunities for collaboration with other scientific communities and research institutions, and potential to contribute to the development of best practices in blue economy research and education.
- **Marginalised groups:** Improved knowledge and awareness of sustainable and circular economy practices, the potential to participate in project design and implementation, and potential to gain access to new economic opportunities and services.

5.1 Drivers and channels

BlueRev will develop and deploy a wide use of channels for reaching out with the aim to communicate and disseminate the project progress to the target groups. These channels will transmit the defined messages and results with the aim to engage the target groups in the implementation, multiplication and mainstreaming of BlueRev. For that reason, the Target groups drivers have been analysed by the partners and specific actions will leverage the use of channels to reach them. Apart from the Website, Social Media and platform of the project (which will be open access), the following strategy will be taken into account:

Table 5-1: Target group Drivers and Channel outreach

TARGET GROUPS	DRIVERS	CHANNEL OUTREACH
National, regional, and local authorities and regional clusters:	Economic development and growth: The BlueRev project focus on promoting sustainable economic growth in coastal and maritime sectors, which can provide new opportunities for economic development and growth in local communities.	Targeted outreach through conferences, workshops, and events, as well as leveraging existing networks such as the European Union's Blue Growth Strategy and the UN's Sustainable Development Goals.
	Environmental conservation: The BlueRev project also aims to promote environmental conservation by promoting sustainable practices in coastal and maritime sectors. For national, regional, and local authorities, this can help protect and restore valuable marine and coastal ecosystems and the services they provide.	
	Policy and regulatory support: The BlueRev project can provide a platform for sharing knowledge and best practices related to policy and regulatory support for sustainable blue economy practices. This can help national, regional, and local authorities develop more effective policies and regulations to support the blue economy.	
Primary biomass producers, associations, and cooperatives:	Market development and growth: The BlueRev project aims to promote the sustainable growth of coastal and maritime industries, which can provide new opportunities for market development and growth for primary biomass producers, associations, and cooperatives.	Targeted outreach through industry associations, newsletters, and online platforms such as LinkedIn or Twitter, as well as partnering with relevant research institutions to demonstrate the potential of new technologies and practices.
	Access to resources and technology: The BlueRev project can provide access to new resources and technologies that can support the sustainable growth and development of coastal and maritime industries. This can help primary biomass producers, associations, and cooperatives to adopt new and more sustainable practices.	

Organizations and SMEs:	Innovation and development: The BlueRev project aims to promote innovation and development in coastal and maritime sectors, which can provide new opportunities for organizations and SMEs to develop new products and services, and to remain competitive in an evolving marketplace.	Targeted outreach through industry associations, online platforms such as LinkedIn or Twitter, and targeted workshops or training programs to build awareness and showcase best practices and case studies.
	Networking and collaboration: The BlueRev project provides a platform for networking and collaboration among organizations and SMEs working in coastal and maritime sectors. This can help foster new partnerships and collaborations and can facilitate knowledge sharing and capacity building.	
Civil society organizations including NGOs:	Community development: The BlueRev project aims to promote community development in coastal and maritime sectors, which can provide new opportunities for civil society organizations and NGOs to engage with local communities and promote social and environmental justice.	Targeted outreach through environmental and sustainability events, partnerships with relevant NGOs or sustainability-focused networks, and leveraging existing partnerships with other organizations or coalitions.
	Advocacy and awareness-raising: Civil society organizations and NGOs can play a critical role in advocating for sustainable practices in coastal and maritime sectors, and in raising awareness of the social and environmental benefits of the blue economy.	
Knowledge providers and scientific communities:	Research and innovation: The BlueRev project can provide new opportunities for knowledge providers and scientific communities to engage in research and innovation related to sustainable coastal and maritime industries.	Targeted outreach through relevant academic conferences, publications, and partnerships with research institutions or universities, as well as leveraging existing partnerships with other knowledge providers. Targeted outreach through scientific conferences, publications, and partnerships with research institutions or universities, as well as leveraging existing partnerships with other scientific communities.
	Capacity building and knowledge sharing: The BlueRev project can provide a platform for knowledge sharing and capacity building among knowledge providers and scientific communities, which can help to promote the development and dissemination of best practices and innovations in coastal and maritime sectors.	
Community knowledge:	Empowerment and engagement: The BlueRev project aims to promote the empowerment and engagement of local communities in coastal and maritime sectors. For community knowledge, this	Targeted outreach through community events, partnerships with local organizations or

	<p>can provide new opportunities to engage with and influence the development of sustainable coastal and maritime industries.</p>	<p>community groups, and engaging community members in project design and implementation.</p>
	<p>Knowledge sharing and capacity building: The BlueRev project can provide a platform for knowledge sharing and capacity building among community knowledge stakeholders, which can help to promote the development and dissemination of best practices and innovations in coastal and maritime sectors.</p>	
<p>Marginalized groups:</p>	<p>Employment opportunities and community development: The BlueRev project focuses on promoting sustainable economic growth and community development in coastal and maritime sectors, which can provide new opportunities for employment and community development for marginalized groups.</p>	<p>Targeted outreach through community events, partnerships with local organizations or community groups, and engaging community members in project design and implementation. Additionally, special attention should be given to making project information accessible through visual and audio formats and translated into local languages.</p>
	<p>Access to resources and education and training: The BlueRev project can provide new opportunities for access to resources and education and training in coastal and maritime sectors, which can help to promote economic and social inclusion for marginalized groups.</p>	

5.2 Stakeholders' mapping and engagement strategies

The involvement of stakeholders is a key element of the BlueRev methodology, as such, we have defined the following objectives and associated steps to ensure a successful engagement of stakeholders.

Each of these strategies is outlined below and followed by a brief description.

Identify stakeholders & target groups and define the level of granularity

Mapping and analysis of regional stakeholders will be conducted under Task 2.1 which will be supported in WP6 to ensure the identification of stakeholders that can support the visibility and dissemination of the project activities.

An initial taxonomy of target groups is outlined in section 5, based on the identification and analysis of target groups categories first identified during the development of the proposal. These categories will be systematically revised and expanded based on inputs from other organisations and contacts identified in the interim period in the early stages of the project.

Identify drivers and the motivational drivers for engaging the different target groups

For developing an efficient engagement strategy, it is important to define the reasons for reaching each type of target groups and identify their driver and motivations, because it allows us to tailor our discussion and messages towards the different types of target groups.

In particular, identifying target groups' motivations and why each stakeholder type should be engaged enables us to make sure that the topics raised by the project match their interests, needs and expectations.

Ultimately, we want to engage target groups in ways that are useful to them, by providing a useful service and encouraging them to continue an active engagement and involvement with BlueRev.

Match the right means and media/channels with the type of target groups.

We have identified the different means to reach the different types of stakeholders, namely communication (e-mails, press releases, articles in dedicated blogs, website, and social media) and dissemination (conferences, workshops, scientific publications).

The project will take this approach in order to optimise project resources and ensure that communications are relevant to as many different categories of stakeholders as possible.

Evaluate the cost-effectiveness of each of the different ways of reaching out to target groups and decide how cost-effectiveness is to be evaluated or measured.

6 BlueRev Partners' support in the project's dissemination and communication

To ensure a collective and efficient flow of dissemination and communication activities, all BlueRev partners will contribute to WP6, therefore, some of the involvement and actions that partners can carry out to contribute to the dissemination of the project are the following:

- Contribute to the project's Social Media channels to keep them active, up-to-date and interesting, by informing the WP6 Leader about relevant content for social media such as events, achievements, or interesting information that should be published in the social media channels;
- Contribute to the project's website and newsletter providing WP6 Leader with relevant news and updates;
- Implement publicity and dissemination campaigns in their own countries/regions and at European level, as well as networks.
 - sharing content posted on BlueRev social media,
 - sharing translated content posted on BlueRev social media,
 - posting content about the project in their own professional or personal channels mentioning @BLUEREVEU or #BLUEREVEU
 - conducting dissemination in their own professional or personal channels (corporate newsletter, blogs, website, etc);
- Exploit their contacts and networks, distributing newsletters, emailing or press releases in their countries/regions;
- Participate in relevant events to promote the project and its outcomes, through presentations, exhibitions, and distributing/displaying promotional material (i.e., brochure, goodies, roll-up, poster...).

7 Project identity

The identity for BlueRev was developed in the first month of the project and will be systematically used in all dissemination and communication actions and materials produced within the frame of the project, such as templates, brochures, website, posters, roll-up banners, videos, etc.

BlueRev brand identity encompasses different noticeable elements (such as colours, font, logo, etc), that can instantly be associated with the project. The development of the project's brand included a thorough background analysis of the project, and assessing the brand values, attributes, positioning and language.

The brand brings together various underlying values, messages and concepts of the project. The main one is the concept of water as an association to the oceans, to the waves of the sea, which is the element that is the basis of the project. Consequently, the three lines of the logo can be associated with the three pillars of the project (namely: social innovation, business models and governance models) and, simultaneously, the various actors involved in it: each of them will be a strong contribution to the project. The general shape of the logo looks like a square with rounded corners, and this reinforces the idea of core and solution. The position of the symbol in the upper right corner resembles the position of a flag that refers to navigation and exploration of the ocean.

Table 7-1: Branding proposal and logo of BlueRev

<p>keywords</p>	<p>blue economy ocean bio-based value chain climate crisis community awareness guidelines knowledge</p>
<p>solution</p>	

The presentation of the identity and concept is available in [Appendix A. Presentation of the identity and concept.](#)

The logo of the project is the following:

Bio-based revitalisation of local communities

Figure 2: BlueRev Logo

The logo is accompanied by the claim “Bio-based revitalisation of local communities”, which aims to clearly transmit the mission and motivational driver of the project.

A brand manual dictating the rules and guidelines on the elements of BlueRev’s identity and how it should be used has also been developed. The logo is available in the SharePoint repository in different versions and formats:

- Logo with and without claim
- Logo in black and colour
- Logo in ai, jpeg, pdf, png, svg formats

The Brand Manual is available in [Appendix B - Brand Manual](#)

8 Channels and Tools

To successfully put into practice the Dissemination and Communication plan, BlueRev will make use of several channels and tools. As the dissemination and communication leader, LOBA will ensure the ongoing synergy between the project's activities to make the most out of the content produced within the project, by communicating the knowledge in different styles (infographics, videos, GIFs, images, etc) using a multichannel approach (website, social networks, media, mailing campaigns, etc). Several tools and channels will be used to support the communication of the right messages to the targeted audiences.

8.1 Website

BlueRev website will provide information about the scope of the project, objectives, main activities, and events, it also gives access to the project's outputs and public results. The website will be used as a means to reach the target groups to be engaged with the project to take actions such as:

- Joining our communities of stakeholders at a regional level
- Participate in our co-creation activities and events
- Use our results
- Be informed and aware of the project

Therefore, all the communication actions implemented during the project will ultimately direct traffic to the website, with the objective of increasing our "conversion rate", which is the number of users or website visitors to take a desired action.

The website will be constantly micro-improved throughout the duration of the project (optimization procedures that do not affect the basic structure), based on Google Analytics and Google Webmaster Tools (including search engine optimisation - SEO).

The main features of the website are the following:

- **RESPONSIVE:** The website platform will suit different devices such as mobile, tablet and desktop;
- **SECURE:** The collection and treatment of data from the visitors will be in compliance with the defined Privacy Policy included in the D2.1;
- **SOCIAL MEDIA SHARING:** The website is prepared to share information with social media networks such as LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook and Instagram;
- **MAILING LIST SUBSCRIPTION:** The website will have available a submission form for newsletter subscription requesting the name and email of the person subscribing.

- **ENGAGEMENT FORM:** The website will have a form for the stakeholders that are interested into getting engaged with the project and included in the activities, as well as joining the stakeholders' board.

The BlueRev website management and update will be an ongoing task and its structure will dynamically evolve together with the project during its lifespan.

After the end of the project the website and all its content will be available for five years.

8.1.1 Settings

The URL (Uniform Resource Locator) defined for the website is www.blurevproject.eu, which focuses on the name of the project.

The domain selected was .eu because it is a European Project and the majority of the target groups are accustomed to such domains.

8.1.2 Splash Page

A landing page or splash page for the BlueRev project was developed by LOBA at an early stage, by month 2 (October 2022). It served as a general introduction to the project while the main website was under development. The page featured the teaser video of the project, a brief introduction of the project, its main goal, geographical scope, main activities, beneficiaries, the consortium, contact information, the project's social media and the EU emblem. The splashpage can be seen saved in an internal domain: <https://blurev.webflow.io/> because now it has been replaced in the official domain by the website of the project.

Figure 3: Screenshots of the Splashpage of the project

8.1.3 Official Website

Through a seamless and smooth transition from the splash page, the website has been launched in M4 (December 2023), in line with what was foreseen by BlueRev's Milestone 7 "Full project website".

The website uses Wordpress as a back-office and the front-end is designed and customized to the project's identity and needs.

The website will be also regularly updated with news, events, relevant findings, achievements, and content extracted from the deliverables and reports. Regular maintenance of the website will be conducted.

8.1.3.1 Website sitemap

The website will feature the following structure:

Figure 4 – Website map

The main sections of the website include:

- The **Homepage** was creatively but objectively designed to showcase the project and attract the visitor to explore the other pages of the website. Four main objectives of the homepage are: i) attract the user to get to know more about BlueRev; ii) give an overview to the pillars that constitute the project’s identity; iii) give access to the recent news/events; iv) provide visible access to social media; v) provide easy access to subscriptions such as to the newsletter or the engagement.
- **About** area with various subsections that provide general information on the project, namely:
 - Project overview with content addressing:
 - Background & Mission: Summary of the challenge addressed by the project, its mission and specific objectives.
 - Action plan: Presents the methodology and main activities of the project.
 - What we fight for: Presents the goals of the project work and what it strives to achieve.
 - **Consortium** aims at presenting the partners composing the consortium with a dedicated page for each of them.
 - **Supporting bodies** aimed at showcasing relevant information about the “Stakeholders Board”.
 - **Synergies** aimed at creating awareness about other EU-funded projects and initiatives with similar goals or complementing activities with BlueRev,

with which the project aims to establish close collaborations and leverage from identified synergies.

- **Pilot Regions** area will be a page dedicated for showing the main project's findings resulting from – and activities carried out for and by – BlueRev's pilot regions; .
- **Support tool** will host the namesake online platform (as for Task 2.3) and allow users to login and to engage in exchange of useful information for the implementation of the piloting and interact with each other. [Further details in Part B of this document](#)
- **Results** area will have functionalities of a platform that will ease the search and find information. This area will be ready and available by the time the project has the first public reports (deliverables) and materials.
- **Press corner** area will comprise three different areas:
 - **News & Articles** showcases all projects news and author articles produced by the partners.
 - **Newsletters** will provide access to the project's newsletters and the form to subscribe to the newsletter.
 - **Press releases** will provide access of press releases already distributed.
- **Events** area will provide information about both upcoming and past events.
- **Contact** area provides information and a form to get in touch with the project. The project has set up the email info@bluerevproject.eu for receiving external communications.

It is implied that, during the project implementation, and according to the needs, activities and ideas that will occur, new sections may be added to the website, and existing ones may be replaced or changed. D6.2 will provide an updated overview and a history of changes for the website map.

8.1.3.2 Analytics and Monitoring

The BlueRev website will use Google Analytics as its web analytics service to track website traffic and assess useful statistics that will help optimise the website and the communication and dissemination strategy. Furthermore, the monitoring process will ensure compliance with GDPR.

Relevant statistics that will be monitored are the following:

- Number of visitors;
- Time spent on the website;
- Returning visitors;
- Number of countries.

8.1.3.3 Website development process

The creation of the website followed a specific process to ensure its quality. Firstly, an internal meeting with LOBA's technicians was conducted in order to present the briefing

with all the features for the website, that were previously agreed upon among the consortium.

Then LOBA developed a wireframe of the website, that was shared with the consortium to show the overall structure of the website and identify any need for alterations or adjustments. In parallel, the contents for the website were developed, in collaboration with BlueRev partners for specific sections.

Then, LOBA worked on the design of the different pages, the front-end development (HTML) of the website, and finally, the development of the back-office of the website.

After each stage of development, a Quality Assurance (QA) procedure was implemented, allowing to detected issues to be corrected. The designer, front-end developer and back-office programmer validated their respective areas. Afterward, two additional Quality Assurance tests were conducted by other people from LOBA. After the final validations, the website was ready to go online, replacing the Splash Page, under the official domain.

8.2 Social Media

BlueRev's official social media pages have already been launched in Month 2 at the same time of the splash page. These include Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn and Facebook. A YouTube channel was also created to serve as a repository of the project's videos.

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/BlueRevEU/>

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/BlueRevEU>

Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/bluereveu/>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/bluereveu>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCCXB2P8XYb3WOz3WqcaWh-w>

The objective of these social media channels is to increase awareness and engagement within the targeted audience.

The handle of the project is the same for all the channels: @BLUEREVEU. For setting up the social media accounts, image banners were designed for the page profile, together with relevant content that concisely inform about the scope of the project. The EU emblem is clearly visible in compliance with the Grant Agreement and the EU guidelines for Horizon Europe projects.

The social media pages of the project will be updated on a weekly basis with posts concerning the project's latest updates, activities, and materials, as well as relevant news and articles regarding the project or posts that tackle common themes. For this, LOBA creates a monthly social media plan with the copy, hashtags, mentions and images/videos per post.

In the first 6 months of the project, 1 post per week has been guaranteed (excluding additional retweets and shares), and after that, once the project will have more content to communicate, LOBA will ensure the publication of 2 posts per week.

Whenever possible, posts related to the project activities, events, and its results, will mention/tag the following accounts from the EC and from key initiatives that can act as multipliers:

- European Commission Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (@EU_MARE) - 32.6k followers (Twitter)
- European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (@EMFFeu) - 6,906 followers (Twitter)
- Blue Growth (@bluegrowthEU) - 3,202 followers (Twitter)
- EU Environment (@EU_ENV) - 58.9k followers (Twitter)
- EU Climate Action (@EUClimateAction) - 294.2k followers (Twitter)
- EU Science Hub - Ocean (@EU_ScienceHub) - 12.8k followers (Twitter)
- EU Maritime Policy (@EU_Maritime) - 9,654 followers (Twitter)
- Copernicus Marine Service (@CopernicusEU) - 27.6k followers (Twitter)
- European Aquaculture Society (@EAS_Society) - 4,764 followers (Twitter)
- Seas At Risk (@seasatrisk) - 4,517 followers (Twitter)
- European Commission (@EU_Commission) - 2.5M followers (Twitter)
- DG MARE (@EU_MARE) - 32.6k followers (Twitter)
- EASME (@EASME_Jobs) - 8,507 followers (Twitter)
- EU Maritime Day (@EUMaritimeDay) - 11.1k followers (Twitter)
- European Innovation Partnership on Water (@eip_water) - 1,527 followers (Twitter)
- EU Science & Innovation (@EUScienceInnov) - 210.9k followers (Twitter)
- European Parliament (@Europarl_EN) - 934.3k followers (Twitter)
- European Council (@EUCouncil) - 767.7k followers (Twitter)
- Clean Energy for EU Islands Secretariat (@CE4EU) - 4,132 followers (Twitter)
- Horizon Europe: @HorizonEU (163.200 followers)
- EU Education and Culture (Erasmus Plus): @EUErasmusPlus (143.800 followers)
- European training Foundation (ETF): @etfeuropa (10.400 followers)
- EU in my region (DG Regional & Urban Policy): @EUinmyRegion (90.700 followers)
- European Parliament Committee on Regional Development: @EP_Regional (7.430 followers)

Some of the LinkedIn groups and Instagram accounts that the project will be linked to and use for communication and dissemination:

- European Blue Growth Community: This is a community of people and organizations working on blue growth initiatives in the EU. It has over 6,000

members and is a great platform to share updates and network with other blue economy stakeholders.

- Sustainable Ocean Alliance: This is a global organization dedicated to advancing ocean health and sustainability. It has over 11,000 members on LinkedIn and is a great platform to share updates related to the BlueRev Project.
- Ocean Energy Europe: This is a trade association for ocean energy in Europe. It has over 1,500 members and is a great platform to share updates related to ocean energy and the BlueRev Project.
- Marine Stewardship Council: This is an international nonprofit organization that sets standards for sustainable fishing. It has over 30,000 members on LinkedIn and is a great platform to share updates related to sustainable fishing and the BlueRev Project.

Instagram:

- European Commission: The European Commission's Instagram account (@europeancommission) has over 200,000 followers and is a great platform to share updates related to the BlueRev Project and other EU initiatives.
- Oceanic Global: Oceanic Global (@oceanic.global) is a nonprofit organization that raises awareness about ocean conservation. It has over 25,000 followers and is a great platform to share updates related to the BlueRev Project and ocean conservation.
- Surfrider Foundation Europe: The Surfrider Foundation Europe (@surfridereurope) is a nonprofit organization dedicated to protecting the ocean and coastlines. It has over 30,000 followers and is a great platform to share updates related to the BlueRev Project and coastal protection.
- Seas At Risk: Seas At Risk (@seasatrisk) is a European network of environmental organizations dedicated to protecting the marine environment. It has over 1,500 followers and is a great platform to share updates related to the BlueRev Project and marine conservation.

Relevant hashtags that will be used in the project:

- #BlueEconomy - 65.8k followers
- #CircularEconomy - 64.6k followers
- #SustainableDevelopment - 62.7k followers
- #HorizonEurope – 167.8k followers
- #MarineScience - 17.1k followers
- #MarineProtection - 5,091 followers
- #SustainableFishing - 1,270 followers
- #OceanRenewableEnergy - 2,691 followers

- #BlueTech - 7,732 followers
- #Aquaculture - 5,273 followers
- #OceanObservation - 1,882 followers
- #OceanGovernance - 9,661 followers
- #MaritimeSpatialPlanning - 1,595 followers
- #BlueGrowth - 7,256 followers
- #MaritimeResearch - 1,204 followers
- #MarineLitter - 3,786 followers
- #OceanProtection - 3,946 followers
- #FisheriesControl - 736 followers
- #EUMaritimeSecurity - 2,291 followers
- #CleanOceans - 3,376 followers

Other handles and hashtags will be included considering the nature of the post.

BlueRev partners are encouraged to use their own (institutional or personal) social media pages to promote BlueRev using its handle (@BLUEREVEU) whenever posting something related to the project through their own channels.

The following table presents the partners' social media accounts as well as their organisations, which BlueRev will follow and mention whenever it is appropriate, BlueRev's communication team can liaise with respective communication departments to ensure their coverage.

Table 8-1: Partners Social Media

#	Partners	Social Media
1	AGENCY FOR THE PROMOTION OF EUROPEAN RESEARCH (APRE) - Italy	Twitter: https://twitter.com/APRE_it
		LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/apre---agenzia-per-la-promozione-della-ricerca-europea/
		Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/APRE.it
2	DISTRICT OF FISHERY AND BLUE GROWTH (DFBG) - Italy	Twitter: https://twitter.com/DistrettoPesca
		LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/distretto-pesca-e-crescita-blu/about/
		Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/DistrettoPescaCrescitaBlu/
3	ESTONIAN UNIVERSITY OF LIFE SCIENCES (EMU) - Estonia	Twitter: https://twitter.com/EULifeSciences
		LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/estonian-university-of-life-sciences/
		Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/eulifesciences

4	FOOD AND BIO CLUSTER DENMARK (FBCD) - Denmark	Twitter: https://twitter.com/foodbiocluster
		LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/food-and-bio-cluster-denmark/
		Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/FBCDenmark/
5	LOBA - Portugal	Twitter: https://twitter.com/loba_cx
		LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/loba-cx
		Facebook: http://www.facebook.com/LOBA.cx
6	NORWEGIAN INSTITUTE OF BIOECONOMY RESEARCH (NIBIO) - Norway	Twitter: https://twitter.com/nibio_no
		LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/nibio/
		Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/NIBIO.no
7	RESEARCH INSTITUTES OF SWEDEN (RISE) - Sweden	Twitter: https://twitter.com/RISEsweden
		LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/research-institutes-of-sweden/
		Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/RISEsweden
8	UNIVERSITY OF AGDER (UIA) - Norway	Twitter: https://twitter.com/uia_norge
		LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/university-of-agder/
		Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/universitetetiagder/

All Social Media visuals will be cohesive, showcasing the project's identity and the EU emblem in compliance with the GA and the EU guidelines for Horizon Europe projects. Therefore, LOBA will design tailored banners, illustrations, GIFs, graphics (etc.) whenever necessary, for posts, or social media profile and cover images.

Paid campaigns (ads) will be built as marketing strategies around three core goals:

- a) enlarge and engage the community,
- b) build email contact list,
- c) increase website traffic.

Instagram, Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn campaigns will unfold whenever BlueRev has important milestones / events / deliverables / achievements to announce.

Social Media statistics will be closely and regularly monitored and analysed, in order to identify any need for improvement or adjust the strategy implemented for each target group.

8.3 Multimedia communication

The project envisages the development of at least 1 promotional video in month 9 aimed at introducing the BlueRev scope and objectives and to encourage stakeholders to join or follow the project activities.

The project has already developed in Month 2 a teaser video of the project aimed at starting to create interest and awareness about the project and expectations about what's to come. This teaser video is available on the project's website via Vimeo embedding ([LINK](#))

Figure 5: Screenshot of BlueRev's teaser video

During the project, it will be expected to produce additional videos, such as recording of co-creation workshops and events (WP2 and WP5), interviews to relevant stakeholders, short animations to showcase key findings and results, also including multimedia contents and a demonstrative video for best practices, lesson recordings and related materials.

All the videos will be uploaded in the YouTube channel, will be shared on the project's digital channels (i.e., website and social media) and will be used in events to promote the project and create awareness.

The production of videos will follow the steps below:

1. Conceptualisation;
2. Pre-Production;
3. Production;
4. Post-Production;
5. Marketing & Distribution support.

In the case of organizer webinars, the recordings of the webinars will be edited as follows:

- Revising and cutting any parts with issues such as technical or connection difficulties.
- Adding a first frame/intro with the animation of BlueRev logo and EU emblem;
- Adding a second frame with the title, date, and speakers of the webinar;
- Adding a last frame with all the website, email, logos of partners, EU emblem.
- Additional editing may be considered case by case.

8.4 Communication toolkit

The communication toolkit developed for the BlueRev project comprises the materials supporting consortium members in their formal and informal communication activities, such as reporting and participation in meetings and events, while ensuring a promotion of the brand identity making it memorable.

This kit is composed by the project's stationery and promotional support materials, as explained below.

8.4.1 Project's stationery

The stationery produced for the project includes materials to support the communication and reporting of the project, namely:

- **Word and power point templates** used for reporting purposes and for presentations at meetings or events, respectively. The background templates used for the branding of these templates can be seen in [APPENDIX D – Backgrounds of the basic templates](#)
- **Supporting materials** for participating in events and meetings such as folders, letterhead paper, badges, business cards, background for online meetings, and an email signature for the identification of the project in communications. These materials can be seen in the [APPENDIX E – Supporting materials](#)

8.4.2 Promotional materials

For promotional purposes, the project is currently developing materials for the promotion of the project during the participation in or organisation of events and meetings with relevant stakeholders. In order to be environmentally conscious, the project supports the “less paper” principle and will encourage the use of digital versions to minimise unnecessary waste of resources.

These materials will include already delivered:

- **Power point presentation** of the project for partners to use when participating in events; This presentation can be seen in [APPENDIX C – Power Point Presentation](#)
- **A graphic kit** to be used in the creation of content for a successful visual promotion. These can be seen in the [APPENDIX F – Graphics kit overview](#)

And also under development:

- **Brochure** with information about the objectives, activities and expected results of the project;

- **Poster, roll-up, sticker, and pop-up stand** to increase the project's visibility in events.

All partners are encouraged to use the communication and promotional materials in their dissemination activities, in order to increase the project awareness and the effectiveness of dissemination actions.

8.4.3 Newsletter and Mass Mailing

BlueRev will distribute a newsletter every 6 months. The consortium will contribute to the development of the contents, and LOBA will ensure the mass distribution of the newsletters to the list of subscribers (complying with GDPR).

The newsletters will be sent proactively to website subscribers, while other synergy projects and partners will be encouraged to share them within their own networks.

Each newsletter can include articles, interviews, videos and infographics and it will be uploaded to the public section of the website. LOBA will keep track and analyse newsletter statistics based on the number of recipients, the number of newsletters opened, the number of clicks, as well as the number of recipients that opened the newsletter and unsubscribed.

The website includes an area to subscribe to the newsletter, the system used for managing and distribution of newsletters is Zoho Campaigns.

In order to maximise the impact of the newsletter, the first one will be launched in Month 9 taking into account that by that month the project results are more advanced and there is more concrete content to develop this resource.

To complement the distribution of newsletters, the project will also send mass mailings with relevant announcements or achievements like events, or surveys. The project will also proactively contribute to the newsletter from other projects with similar goals and target groups as BlueRev, in order to increase visibility and reach.

9 Events

In the context of BlueRev implementation, it is possible to differentiate between “internal” and “external” events, according to the further explanations and details provided down below.

The “**internal events**” refer to the events that will be organised during the project under the frame of specific work packages (WP1, WP3, WP4 & WP5). These “internal events” have their specific purposes for technical aspects of the project, but they are also a good opportunity for communicating and disseminating the project. In this context, WP6 will support the partners in communicating these events, engaging potential participants and disseminating the outcomes from those events.

The strategy and methodology of the internal events are currently being defined under the respective WPs, therefore the following information is subject to alteration.

Table 9-1: Internal events

WPs/partners responsible	Type of event	Number of events	KPI	Description
WP1	KoM	1	1	Kick-off meeting to start the project
WP1	Physical project meetings	1 per year	1 per year	Project meetings to assess the status of the project
WP3	Workshop	3	at least 10 participants per workshop	Workshops aiming at helping local stakeholders to analyse social and economic barriers and potentialities in their regions to enable the transition towards socially and environmentally responsible behaviour through new business models, informed governance and especially social innovation developed within the project
WP4	Workshop	3	at least 10 participants per workshop	Workshops aiming at helping local stakeholders to analyse social and economic barriers and potentialities in their regions to enable the transition towards socially and environmentally responsible behaviour through new business models, informed governance and especially social innovation developed within the project
WP5	Workshop	3	50- 100 participants each	Three workshops (~50-100 participants each) to transfer the new solutions to all the stakeholders (in and outside the pilot regions) under a fully transferable case-study approach, that can be replicated in many other regions throughout EU

DFBG	Training module	3 lessons	100-200 participants	Training directed to increase small-scale establishments in the bioeconomy
DFBG	training module	3 lessons		Training/coaching programme to increase skilled job opportunities
EMÜ, UiA	training module	3 lessons		Training directed to increase small-scale establishments in the bioeconomy and to increase skilled job opportunities.
APRE	training module	4 webinars		Training directed to increase small-scale establishments in the bioeconomy

The “**external events**” refer to events organised by others where BlueRev partners can participate to disseminate the project. Workshops, booths, and networking events are important for increasing the project’s awareness within specific target groups and presenting the project’s mission, activities and results. This includes for example workshops and cluster meetings arranged by the EC, other projects/initiatives and European fairs/exhibitions.

The following list provides possible events that will be considered.

1. European Maritime Day: May 24-25, 2023; Best, France
2. Ocean Business: April 18-20, 2023; Southampton, UK
3. Europort: November 7-10, 2022; Rotterdam, Netherlands
4. BlueInvest Day: March 9, 2023; Brussels, Belgium
5. Seawork International: June 13-15, 2023; Southampton, UK
6. Oceanology International: March 12-14, 2024; London, UK
7. AquaNor: August 22-24, 2023; Trondheim, Norway
8. European Aquaculture Society Conference: September 18-21, 2023; Austria, Vienna
9. European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference: September 5-9, 2023; Portsmouth, England
10. Sustainable Ocean Summit
11. UN 2023 Water Conference 22 — 24 Mar 2023, New York
12. International Marine Renewable Energy Conference: September 10-20, 2023; Edinburgh, Scotland
13. BlueTech Global Connect: monthly webinars
14. World Ocean Summit: 27 February till 1 March, 2023; Lisbon, Portugal

Also, the partners will be paying attention to upcoming events appearing in the list <https://medblueconomyplatform.org/vkc/events/>

The project will utilize also a shared document available in SharePoint for sharing relevant events identified by partners or events that partners are planning to participate.

9.1 Events’ communication “before, during and after”

The communication and promotion of BlueRev events or partners' participation in events will follow a specific strategy. These actions will be implemented in the promotion of the events, whenever applicable. They will be adjusted depending on the needs and type of involvement of BlueRev (i.e., organiser, participant, attendee).

- Communication BEFORE the event:
- Event upload on the website
- Design of cover image or banner, or other images/videos
- Social media campaign
- Publication in the Newsletter
- Press release (if applicable)
- Mass mailing to BlueRev mailing list
- BlueRev partners dissemination through their networks and channels

Communication DURING the event:

- Social media coverage (photos/quotes sent to LOBA for posting)
- Networking and distribution of promotional materials

Communication AFTER the event:

- Article upload in website (Conclusions, photos, presentations, recording, etc)
- Event recording uploaded in YouTube channel (for online events when applicable)
- Social media campaign
- Publication in the Newsletter

10 Joint communication & dissemination with other projects

Liaison with other projects and initiatives is an enormous added value of EU funded projects, since similar, complementary, or related projects and organisations can be used as multipliers instead of competitors (through link exchange strategies, collaboration in events, social media collaborations, creation of articles and blogposts, etc.).

For BlueRev project liaison with existing projects and networks, and more specifically with projects funded under the topic of HORIZON-CL6-2021-COMMUNITIES-01-02: Expertise and training centre on rural innovation is an important component.

In this context, the Task 6.4 “Networking with other projects/initiatives” (led by LOBA), will establish the strategy and actions to create international and inter-project collaboration and targeted knowledge exchange with EU-funded projects, networks and institutes.

This strategy will be designed by all partners and will be focused in two main steps, leveraging the existing connections and networks of all partners and desk-based research to identify and map the various networks that currently exist in Europe.

An action plan is being drafted:

1. All partners with the coordination of LOBA will further the initial mapping of complementary EU projects, in particular the ones funded under the HORIZON-CL6-2021-COMMUNITIES-01-02: Expertise and training centre on rural innovation is an important component.
2. LOBA will develop a collaboration memorandum of understanding where will be stated who, how, when and what type of synergy will be developed between projects.
3. LOBA developed a dedicated area on the project’s website – Synergies page, where a specific template can be filled with information about the projects that are collaboration with BlueRev.
4. LOBA will inform projects and initiatives collaborating with BlueRev when the project’s Newsletters are being released and give the option to contribute with news.
5. LOBA will follow, share and engage with the project’s collaborations with BlueRev through their social media channels.
6. Opportunities to participate in each other external events and initiatives will be discussed

11 Reporting procedure

In order to guarantee a successful dissemination of the BlueRev project as well as an efficient reporting process within the participant portal, partners are asked to fill in a form for monitoring the communication and dissemination activities and their impact.

Following the new updates in the participant portal “continuous reporting”, the procedure used in BlueRev for reporting C&D activities has been aligned with the fields requested by the EU, but also includes additional information relevant to assessing the performance of C&D activities.

The participant portal has now two areas, one for communication activities and another for dissemination activities. According to several EC guidelines¹, and information in the participant portal, the concepts of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation are defined as follows.

Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation	
Reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities, e.g. by addressing and providing possible solutions to fundamental societal challenges.	Transfer knowledge & results with the aim to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximising the impact of EU-funded research.	Effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes aiming to turn R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society.	Objective
Inform about and promote the project AND its results/success.	Describe and ensure results available for others to USE → focus on results only!	Make concrete use of research results (not restricted to commercial use.)	Focus
Multiple audiences beyond the project's own community incl. media and the broad public.	Audiences that may take an interest in the potential USE of the results (e.g. scientific community, industrial partner, policymakers).	People/organisations including project partners themselves that make concrete use of the project results, as well as user groups outside the project.	Target Audience

Figure 6: Slide from the EC presentation "Introduction to the concepts of Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation"

Communication activities are those aimed at promoting the action and its results. These activities require strategic and targeted measures for communicating about i) the action and ii) its results to a multitude of audience, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/other/event210609.htm>

Therefore, communication activities are those that create awareness and inform about the project's objectives, scope and mission, activities and results, and engage stakeholders to participate in events/activities.

Dissemination activities have a stronger focus on disseminating knowledge and results towards their actual use, in a targeted manner to specific beneficiaries or potential end-users, i.e., knowledge transfer, scientific publications, use or replicability of results/methodologies, lessons learned, data, etc.

In this sense, BlueRev has developed a shared excel document that will be used by partners to report their C&D activities.

- Access to the excel for reporting [HERE](#)

The instructions and information requested in the document is the following: The document is divided into 3 spreadsheets (Communication, Dissemination and Publications):

DISSEMINATION Spreadsheet:

Column A. partner: This is the main partner responsible of the activity and the one inserting the information in the form.

Column B. Date: Indicate the date when the activity took place. (In the case of events, we will be asking the duration later on, so no need to put start & end date here).

Column C. Place: Indicate the place where the activity was implemented, city/ country, or if it was online.

Column D. Dissemination Activity Name: Provide a name for the activity that you implemented.

Column E. WHY? DESCRIPTION of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters).

Column F: WHAT? Select the type of dissemination activity (Conferences, Education and training events, Meetings, Clustering activities, Collaboration with EU-funded projects, Other scientific collaboration, Other scientific cooperation, Other)

Column G: Who? Target audience reached - you can SELECT MORE THAN ONCE in each cell, from the options (Research communities, Industry business partners, Innovators, Investors, International organisation (UN body. OECD. etc.), EU Institutions, National authorities, Regional authorities, Local authorities, Civil society, Citizens, Specific end user communities, Other)

Column H: Impact: Fill in an estimation of the number of individuals that were reached.

Column I: Status: Fill in the status of the activity by selecting form the available options (Cancelled, Delivered, Ongoing, Postponed)

COMMUNICATION Spreadsheet:

Column A. Partner: This is the main partner responsible for the activity and the one inserting the information in the form.

Column B. Date: Indicate the date when the activity took place. (In the case of events, we will be asking the duration later on, so no need to put start & end date here).

Column C. Place: Indicate the place where the activity happened, by mentioning city, country, or if it was online.

Column D. Communication Activity Name: Provide a name for the activity that you implemented.

Column E. Description: Provide a description of the activity that you implemented.

Column F. Communication channels: Select the option that applies: (Event, Exhibition, Interview, Media article, Newsletter, press release, Print materials, Social media, TV Radio campaign, Video, Website, Other).

Column G. Who? Target audience: Select the target audiences. Here you can SELECT MORE THAN ONCE in each cell from the provided options (Citizens, Civil society, EU institutions, Industry, Innovators, International organisation, Investors, Local authorities, National authorities, Regional authorities, Research communities, Specific end user communities).

Column H. Outcome: Fill in an estimation of the number of individuals that were reached.

Column I: Status: Fill in the status of the activity by selecting from the available options (Cancelled, Delivered, Ongoing, Postponed)

PUBLICATIONS Spreadsheet:

Column A: Responsible partners

Column B: Full paper information (Title)

Column C: Link to download paper

Column D: Date of paper

Column E: Open Access (Yes/No)

Column F: Context of paper (Conference, Journal, other)

11.1 Evaluation criteria – Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

In the Description of Action (DoA), a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been described in order to monitor the performance of the activities of the project including dissemination and communication. Therefore, the table below shows the overview of all the Key Performance Indicators of the project as stated in the DoA

Table 11-1: List of Key Performance Indicators

Communication activities Objectives and measurable results	Objectives and measurable results
Realisation of a project logo, brochures, and other communication materials, containing a description of the project activities, objectives, results and expected impacts on the stakeholders.	Project logo, leaflet and brochure, poster.
A specific Media Plan focused on delivering press releases after the achievement of certain milestones.	At least 6 press releases published on different broadcasts.
The BlueRev project website.	Project website available at month 4, continuously updated, target at least 10,000 visitors by project end.
Quarterly newsletter with the relevant information for the bioeconomy stakeholders.	6 published and distributed newsletters starting in M6. Target at least 500 subscribers.
Digital communication on social networks: LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, blogs etc.	Creation of profiles on social media (target 1,000 social media followers) and use of the partners' channels to promote BlueRev.
Leveraging on BlueRev partners' network of organisations and individuals to disseminate the targeted communications that serves to generate more leads to the platform.	Each partner will promote BlueRev through its networks, including websites, newsletters, organisation of local events, targeting at least 3,000 recipients.
A video showing the main feature of the information system that will be widely distributed through the BlueRev website and other social media, such as YouTube.	At least 1 video with 2,000+ views.
Presentation of the BlueRev results in external events and fairs (e.g., Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy Conference; International BioEconomy Conference; IFIB, EFIB, Ecomondo, etc.)	At least 12 presentations in external events, targeting at least 3,000 attendees.
Publication in scientific journals: e.g., Journal of Agricultural And Food Chemistry, European Food Research And Technology; International Journal of Food Science, International Journal of Biological Macromolecules; Process Biochemistry; Journal of Cleaner Production and the International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment.	At least 12 publications, targeting minimum 2,000 readers.

12 Time plan

This section presents the time plan for the development of the main channels, materials, and tools for BioGov.net dissemination and communication strategy. The timeline only includes the tools that will be produced in the first year, and will be updated during the project:

Table 12-1: Indicative time plan for the 1st year

	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
Identity & brand manual	X											
Stationery (Templates & supporting materials)		X										
Splash Page		X										
Social Media channels		X										
Teaser video	X											
Website				X								
Promotional Materials (Brochure, poster...)							X					
Promotional video									X			
1st Newsletter									X			
Press Release										X		

13 Dissemination & Communication plan Conclusions

To successfully disseminate and communicate the BlueRev project, a consistent brand with a strong mission, supported by useful tools, fed with attractive content, and driven by fully committed partners is key. Therefore, all partners are encouraged and committed to contribute and share information about the BlueRev project in order to provide the best content possible.

This document will be updated regularly during the project, the activities will be reported together with relevant updates to the strategy within the respective periodic reports, as well as under D6.3 “Updated plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities” [M19].

14 PART B – SUPPORT TOOL

14.1 Introduction

This Part of the document describes the conceptualization and the action plan for the development of a support tool that will enable the BlueRev stakeholders to operate within the project goals of Piloting. The online tool is referred to as the result of the Task 2.3 Support tool (Task leader: LOBA, Partners involved: all) (M1-M36).

It is meant to be an Open Space that will contain all materials developed within the project, including multimedia contents and demonstrative videos for best practices implemented, lessons recordings and related materials, best practices guidelines etc., and standard info i.e. project and partners, calendar of events, news, etc., by facilitating cross-sector collaborations among stakeholders in the bio-based economy and to provide a knowledge centre to share relevant project results.

This web-based platform will be able to facilitate cross-sector collaborations among stakeholders in the value chains of the blue bio-based economy and will be set up to provide a knowledge centre to i) share relevant information, ii) make stakeholders aware about the possibilities offered by the uptake of the bioeconomy, ii) enhance cooperation opportunities, iii) train stakeholders, iv) allow collaboration and documents exchange among stakeholders.

14.2 Main requirements

As seen above, the purpose of the Support Tool is to host online a space for mutual exchange, collaboration, communication and training that will empower the stakeholders to achieve the envisioned results in their communities. Four types of users are expected to frequent the tool and make the best of its use: Company managers (including NGOs, Social enterprises etc), Policy makers, Trainers, and Project partners.

- As a main aspiration, the support tool will revitalize the way that the local communities collaborate, by spreading the BlueRev knowledge and methodology between the stakeholders through training, communication, and inspiration;
- The interface of the Support Tool will be created from scratch and built in a way that facilitates the users' valorization of the tools and functionalities offered;
- The core functions of the Support tool will be i) access to training resources ii) access to webinars iii) uploading of best practices iv) visualization of video gallery v) access to project results vi) communication between users.
- The branding and the design will follow the defined, detailed project branding guide (with extensive information about the use of the logo).
- Accessible from: iOS, Android, or Windows

14.3 Support tool Objective(s)

Through the BlueRev Support Tool, the variance of identified users is expected to interact in an online interface that sets the ground for the achievement of the following objectives:

Company managers (including NGOs, Social enterprises etc):

- To reinforce awareness of the need for change in order to sustainably grow within the Blue Economy
- To access important resources that arm them with the knowledge to redesign their value propositions and promote local growth
- To get inspired from implemented good cases, and to share their stories to inspire others

Policymakers:

- To come in contact with companies in their area and interact for the promotion of local growth
- To redesign their agendas in order to support sustainable innovation in their communities working hand in hand with the enterprises and associations related to Blue Activities
- To support the Blue Economy revitalization

Trainers:

- To come in contact with companies that need training in order to redefine their business models
- To use the tool's full functionalities in order to reach out European-wide to the pilot countries and share their teachings
- To improve their training impact through the added value of using technological means to reach out to people needing training

Project partners:

- To coordinate the implementation of the pilot with the regions
- To access the analytics and improve the functionalities in order to grow the stakeholders' database
- To push forward the project multiplication and mainstreaming to the target groups
- To grasp the needs of the stakeholders and to connect them with the project's materials

14.4 Layout

For the achievement of the above objectives, the Support Tool will engage the identified users by offering access privileges as identified below:

- Company managers: Access to all pages
- Policy makers: Access to all pages
- Trainers: Access to all pages
- Project partners: Access to all pages

Table 14-1: Support tool outline of pages and user access

	Landing	Homepage	Training	Inspiration	E-Library	Community	Profile
Companies managers	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Policy makers	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Trainers	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Project Partners	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

14.5 List of Features

Table 14-2: Features of the Support Tool

FEATURE	Description
Sign-up and login	Sign-up / login as: Company manager (C), Policy maker (P), Trainer (T), Project partner (B)
Navigation	After login the users will be able to view the main menu and navigate in the pages that are accessible to them.
E learning	Access to lessons (mainly videos and manuals) that are designed for the implementation of the piloting
Webinars	Allowing the conduction of webinars online that the users can watch in live or as a recording
Multimedia gallery	Uploading of multimedia resources to create portfolios of inspirational practices
Community use	Feature allowing the exchange of communication between the members (messaging and chatting as well as forum).
E-library	Online library with uploaded resources for the project specs and guides to replicate the methodologies (support for multimedia material)
Rating and commenting	Every inspirational practice case will have the possibility to be rated and commented

Analytics	Summary of the analytics of the platform use and access
Gamification of use	User badges to incentivize the user to frequent as much as possible the platform and interact with the contents and the users
User profile analytics and ranking	User profiles will showcase their statistics (Number of rates, number of comments and engagement) and ranking will be possible according to a formula to decide the most active users
Social media feed	Side bar on the main pages that gives in social media feed (Facebook)
Invite function	Ability to generate a fast invite to friends/share of the Support Tool, with simple clicks of button
Dropdown menu	When the cursor passes over a menu object in landing page the subpages appear as dropdown
Resources teaser	limited access to only a preview part of the resources if someone is not logged in

14.6 Further information on the pages and the functions

14.6.1 Landing page

Description:

The landing page, is similar to the homepage in the sense that it is a brief window of the Support tool contents with the aim to connect the user with the tool and give a quick idea of what to expect to see inside. The main focus is on the links to materials and resources preview, and the **Join button**. If the user chooses to click the Join in, then a popup window will be enabled to follow up on this activity. This page is a “buy-in of the user”.

Objectives:

- Brief showcase of the Support Tool contents,
- Buy-in users to Sign up and join the Support Tool
- Login place

Contents:

- Login button
- Join button
- Recent News big slider with image and description
- Explanation of the functions with text and graphics
- Numbers of the platform (users, resources, lessons, best practises etc)
- Most recent inspirational videos carousel
- News recent posts (feed from the website BlueRev)
- Events recent posts (feed from the website of BlueRev)
- Social media feed

14.6.2 Homepage

Description:

The homepage is the 1st personalised page the user encounters after the login. It welcomes them and provides them a fast overview of what changed since the last time they logged in.

Objectives:

- 1st contact with the Main Menu
- Connection to the Support Tool contents prompting the user to navigate
- Showcase of the latest updates that happened

Contents:

- Logout button
- Welcome messages
- Main menu
- News big slider with images and descriptions
- Boxed texts with links to resources
- Icon links to the specific contents and a small explanation of each
- Latest news and events

14.6.3 Training

Description:

This page is featuring the training opportunities that are accessible to the user.

Objectives:

- Personalize the training material according to the user
- Give access to the training contents
- Guide the user in the learning process according to their needs
- Connect the user to the webinars

Contents:

- My training área
- Upcoming webinars área
- Learning management interface
- Lessons in Multimedia formats
- Webinar access

14.6.4 Inspiration

Description:

The page builds up inspiration to the users by sharing in multimedia formats the best practices that were implemented. It supports video, documents, and text and the users can upload their inputs and also comments on others.

Objectives:

- Build inspiration for the implementation of BlueRev
- Share, like, and comment on inspirational practices
- Upload your own unique case

Contents:

- Banner for the gallery
- Filters
- Multimedia gallery, with boxed cases, that open to page that can include title, description, video, text and uploads

14.6.5 E-Library

Description:

The page where the useful to the implementation resources will be uploaded. This will allow all users to access and read the project material and get a better grasp of the BlueRev methodology and vision.

Objectives:

- Provide resources that support the users to understand the project
- Support the implementation by linking actions to resources that are uploaded
- Showcase the project advancement and make publicly available the results to all the stakeholders.

Contents:

- Banner
- Details of the library's purpose
- Areas division where the resources listed under these are helping towards specific goals. EG there can be an area for Updating business models, where the resources related to this (methodology etc) are listed under that.

14.6.6 Community

Description:

The community page is following a social media logic that allows the users to see others' profiles and connect in order to talk in synchronous or asynchronous time.

Objectives:

- Communication between users
- Exchange of experiences
- Creation of new collaborations

Contents:

- Social feed
- Areas of interest for discussions
- Messaging

14.6.7 Profile

Description:

The profile page allows the user to customize their virtual avatar and insert descriptions, as well as see their badges that are won according to their amount of engagement.

Objectives:

- To get the users more engaged
- To personalize the Support Tool experience
- To gamify the engagement

Contents:

- Profile admin area
- Profile description
- User statistics and badges
- Analytics of the platform

14.7 Product & Technical Specifications

The website will be accessible from any system with a recent web browser (ex.: Google Chrome, Firefox, Safari, ...).

15 PART C – Exploitation and sustainability initial guidelines

15.1 Introduction

The part C of this document entails the BlueRev Exploitation guidelines that aim to kick-start the formulation of the related strategy, and set the foreground for the creation of the Final Exploitation and Replication Plan (D6.3), due in M36. Thus, it provides an initial introduction to the definitions that the partnership commonly understands, as well as some first tools that partners will use to conceptualize their actions. This plan reinforces important terms that are related to the project success during and after its end, referring mainly to the Exploitation, and tightly driven by the need for Valorisation and Sustainability that will come as a result of a well-designed strategy and implemented actions. During the project course, two more related deliverables will be utilized to set the stage for an even more successful Exploitation, Valorisation and Sustainability, namely referring to:

- “Updated plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities” (D6.2, M18) → This deliverable has been scheduled on a strategic point of the project progress, that allows the partnership to review the implementation and come up with concrete suggestions for the boosting of the Exploitation, Valorisation and Sustainability. Already in M18 the project will have more concrete results to present and more intense collaborations with stakeholders to utilize, thus a more concrete strategy is expected to emerge.
- “Final Exploitation and replication plan” (D6.3, M36) → This deliverable at the end of the project will be the most important document to ensure the viability of the work done, and thus a great level of commitment will be drawn from the partnership for its successful implementation beyond the funding period.

15.2 Adopted definitions

15.2.1 Exploitation

Exploitation is associated with the use of the project’s results at different levels, during and after the implementation of the project. It is related to the necessary action that will bring visibility to the project in order to involve the target groups, end-users, stakeholders and transfer the results/products into their professionals’ scope. Exploitation is mostly related to the idea of convincing the key actors to use the main products of a project. Exploitation is closely associated with the sustainability of the project after its conclusion since exploitation activities should ensure that the results of the project are used by its target groups and possibly are transferred to other contexts (e.g. other countries; other pedagogical areas, other sectors).

The exploitation is split into two components: mainstreaming and multiplication. Mainstreaming means to address the decision-makers in order to convince them to introduce/take into account the results/products of a project, while multiplication is more focused on persuading individual end-users to adopt those products. This usage can be within the partnership and outside, at the local, regional, national, or European level. As in the case of dissemination, the exploitation process should be planned and organised at the beginning of the project by a methodological document (e.g. Exploitation Strategy) that orientates the whole consortium.

15.2.2 Valorisation

Valorisation is a term that includes dissemination and exploitation, and it aims to make the project result/product more valuable to everybody, meaning make “others” use the product. Valorisation is the sum of both dissemination and exploitation activities. The overall objective of valorisation activities is to promote the project and its results and foster their use by different individuals and organisations, with the attempt to constantly spread and improve the usage and the content of the results. Valorisation involves not only the testing and dissemination of the results of the most innovative projects but also the exploitation of these results and their development in new contexts and environments. It includes the sustainable application of these results over time in formal and informal systems, in the practices of organisations as well as in the personal learning goals of every individual. The two main benefits of valorisation are the return enhancement on public and private investments in the area of training/education as well as innovation in training and educational systems. These benefits easily explain why it is recognised as a clear and increased political importance of valorisation in Europe. Valorisation means planning in such a way that the resources affected to a project generate results that can be used and exploited on a large scale, with the view of benefiting as many individuals and organisations as possible. Valorisation must be based on a meticulous ex-ante analysis of needs to be fulfilled by a project as well as on a clear identification of the results expected and this from the right beginning. Effective valorisation requires the active involvement, at the project design stage, of the potential users and target groups who are to benefit from the project and who are ultimately expected to exploit the results.

15.2.3 Sustainability

Sustainability is the capacity of the project to continue its existence and functioning beyond its end. The project results are used and exploited continuously. Sustainability of results implies the use and exploitation of results in the long term. A project can be considered as sustainable if its outcomes continue after the end of EU funding. As the sustainability of project outcomes may be difficult to anticipate and to describe – most are not tangible, this Initial Plan focuses on the sustainability of products and results.

Sustainability may not concern all the aspects of a project. In each project, some results may be maintained, while others may not be so necessary to maintain. A project can, therefore, be considered as sustainable if relevant results are pursued and products are maintained or developed after the end of the EU funding (i.e. duration of new courses, updating of new tools). It is not easy to achieve a plan in order to generate the desired sustainability of the project and somehow ensure a return on investment at European level by multiplying the benefits that the assimilation of best practices can provide. Hence, this is often one of the project weaknesses, and simultaneously one aspect that EU values most.

15.3 Purpose of the Exploitation guidelines

The BlueRev Exploitation guidelines set the ground to start the formulation of a strategy towards clearly described aims and objectives, defined targeted groups, tools for mainstreaming and upscaling the results as well as action plans that will guarantee the Valorisation, Multiplication and Sustainability of the project.

The exploitation strategy will be in line with the needs of the fulfillment of the contractual expectations that respond to:

- European Commission's (EC) requirement to communicate the consortium's strategy and report on planned exploitation activities;
- Consortium partners need to inform about participants' required activities and responsibilities concerning the exploitation of the results after the project ends.

According to the Mainstreaming and Multiplication terms defined by the EU, and adopted within the BlueRev project proposal, the exploitation strategy, and its implementation within else will be also unfolded on two fronts:

- On the one hand, activities targeting the involvement of decision-makers at the political level in order to ensure mainstreaming of the project results;
- On the other hand, activities will be targeted at spreading project results among end-users and at promoting their use, satisfying the multiplication perspective.

For the above to succeed, the project coordinator and all the partners and key actors need to embrace exploitation as a process that reaches beyond the life of the project so that its results are sustained:

“The goal of the exploitation strategy and its implementation plan is, therefore, to explain how during and after the end of the project the results will be exploited to make them sustainable.”

The exploitation plan sets out the activities related to and facilitating, the exploitation of the results by the end and/or potential users and for the benefit of target groups clearly identified from the project design stage. To achieve these goals during the implementation, it elaborates the following issues:

- Define clearly and keep on identifying the target groups/end users/public and political stakeholders of the project's results;
- Ensure that these identified target groups/end users/public and political stakeholders will be involved during the lifetime of the project;
- Clarify how, during and after the end of the project, the results will be exploited and sustained;
- Guarantee that the project results are available and visible after project conclusion;
- Ensure that the network created by the project is enriched sustainably;
- Ensure that the transfer of knowledge and good practices are set up.

Moreover, the initial Exploitation Plan provides an overview of the BlueRev activities and results. It aims to be used as a guide to all partners to highlight the details on partners' activities and responsibilities' after the official date of the end of the project. The specific objectives of the Exploitation activities are:

- To promote and raise awareness about the project contents, developments, and results;
- To successfully transfer the results to appropriate decision-makers to achieve their sustainable promotion and support;
- To convince end-users to adopt and/or apply the results, also after the project and support by its partnership has ended.

15.4 Target audiences

Figure 7: BlueRev target groups clustering

The target audiences are defined and approached under the two different perspectives, for Mainstreaming the results and Multiplication. According to this, the first group described below, as closer to the policy-making, is to be approached with a mindset and actions that foster the Mainstreaming of the BlueRev results:

- National authorities
- Regional authorities
- Local authorities

Moreover, BlueRev partners will pursue the use of the results by the following target groups that will be encouraged to adopt the innovations that were introduced by the BlueRev project and thus satisfy the multiplication needs:

- Knowledge providers
- Scientific communities
- Community knowledge
- Associations
- Cooperatives
- Regional clusters
- Civil Society Organizations
- NGOs
- Marginalized groups
- SMEs
- Primary Biomass Producers

15.5 IPR Management Strategy

Under the frame of BlueRev and for the aforementioned strategic targets of Exploitation, Sustainability and Valorization of the project methodology and results, key IP and innovation management will be employed, with a view to setting a common understanding concerning the background, foreground, ownership (including joint ownership), access and usage rights, dissemination and exploitation during and after the project development. In this respect, the BlueRev IPR management strategy will apply a comprehensive framework which will separate the IP management processes of the project in the following stages:

- Grant Agreement preparation stage;
- Project implementation stage;
- Post-project stage.

In this respect, the following figure illustrates the IPR management stages, as will be considered and followed within BlueRev. More details about these stages will be developed in later timing of the implementation and in the following deliverables

Figure 8: The BlueRev stages of IPR definition and implementation

15.6 IPR Matrix Methodology

The BlueRev IPR management approach foresees the utilization of an IPR Matrix in order to define the main IPR issues concerning the BlueRev Innovation and IPR Management Strategy. This approach will be supported by all project partners in identifying and managing the background, foreground knowledge and exploitable results of the project, and also of potential co-innovators, in order to have a full overview of IP protection and necessary agreements to enable successful exploitation of the project's offerings. The IPR Matrix methodology will be comprised of 4 distinct but interconnected steps, as follows:

- Step 1: Identification of the background IP and definition of access rights among partners within the project.
- Step 2: Identification of the assets and results, which constitute the foreground IP of the project and are generated under the BlueRev activities.
- Step 3: Identification of the project's exploitable results/assets and the corresponding interest for their further exploitation along with the contributing partners to each result.
- Step 4: Definition of a framework of IPR protection for the identified BlueRev assets, to enhance their further exploitation.

Under this framework, the structure of the IPR Matrix that will be used in the future months is summarised below.

Table 15-1: Structure of the IPR Matrix

Background (BG)	Foreground (FG)	Exploitable results (ER)
-----------------	-----------------	--------------------------

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BG# • Partner's Background • Contributing Partner • Short Description of BG • Type of Protection • Conditions to Use within BlueRev • Conditions to use outside BlueRev • Interest in further exploitation through BlueRev results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FG# • Project Result • Related WP • Contributing Partners • Short Description of FG • Related BG# • Type of Protection • Conditions to Use within BlueRev • Interest in further exploitation of Project Results • Conditions to use after the end of the Project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ER# • Exploitable result • Main partner • Further contributing partner(s) • Related FG# • Related BG# • Proposition for the ER-owner • Short description of the ER • Relevance for IP Protection • Exploitation claims • Exploitation. Routes and action plan
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15.7 Re-cap of the BlueRev promo-toolkit

A wide set of tools will be used by the partnership to support the mainstreaming and multiplying of the main results of the project, within these tools having the:

Figure 9: CDE schematic

15.7.1 Website & Support tool

The project's window for the community is the website - <https://www.blurevproject.eu/> , and the tool for its upscaling is the Support Tool that will be developed in a subdomain and will be open access to the consortium members and the public.

The website serves as a presentation of the project, its aims and objectives, materials, and consortium members.

The Support Tool is the tool for implementing the Piloting and supports the participants in their journey.

LOBA will assume the maintenance of the website and the Support Tool for at least 5 years after the end of the project.

Additionally, the project coordinator and partners' contacts will be available in both platforms in case a potential user needs further information about the project.

15.7.2 Social media networks

The social media are populated with online “alive” activity and show that BlueRev is not only contributing to the sector but also staying up-to-date with the news.

The social media pages ([Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Twitter](#), [Instagram](#) as well as [YouTube](#)) are fed constantly not only with the main results and news of the project but also with scientific articles, videos, and other multimedia resources closely related to the Blue Economy sector.

15.7.3 Briefings, Leaflets and brochure

Digital and printable materials will be created to present the project activities, methodology and results in a brief and visually attractive way, ideal to be used during physical encounters with the target groups. These visual tools will be designed to be distributed among events, conferences, meetings, and trainings, for leveraging the exploitation potential of the project’s results and offerings.

15.7.4 Participation in Events, Workshops, and Conferences

All partners will organise/participate in several events aimed at disseminating the project activities and its results. The events can be formal and informal, aiming to encourage people of various backgrounds and disciplines to take part in the discussions. Other future events and also direct contacts and meetings with stakeholders will be very important to promote the sustainability of the project results.

15.7.5 Partners’ networks

Exploitation activities will be mostly based on existing partner networks: all partners cooperate or are in close contact with the target users of the project results. All these target groups will be engaged to contribute to the project activities in all phases of the project.

15.7.6 Further improvement of project results

There is always space for improvement, especially in the actual globalized world. The technological proceedings and innovations, the market needs are continuously changing the sector. Partners will continue to uphold a transnational dialogue to keep updated on the BlueRev results.

15.8 Action suggestions for the partnership

15.8.1 Transfer and follow-up projects

Transfer enhances good practices by spreading results. The transfer can take place at all levels and the results can be used into new contexts or other organisations can customise the results to suit their conditions. And do not forget, submitting a proposal to a call for an exploitation project, can be a smart way of attracting more funding and a wider audience for your hard work. Follow up projects – after a project has finalised its results, it would be best sustained if partnership finds a way to build upon these results and expand the scope of what has already been achieved. Possibilities for doing this would be transfers of innovation or another form of continuation of completed projects.

15.8.2 Sustainability

Just because a project is completed, it does not mean its results disappear. It is important to keep them visible and available, especially through websites, so that target audiences can access them, learn from them, adapt them to their own needs and even build on them and take them to the next level. And of course both transfer and commercialisation support sustainability. The continuity of the project started already very early when choosing the partnership! What to achieve, whom to reach and the stakeholders were clearly defined and established from the right beginning and if the target groups want and need the products, then the project will have a greater chance of survival after the end of the funding period! Where possible collect sustainable declarations, written and signed statements in which individuals/organisations explain how they intend to use/are using the products. If the declarations are obtained during the project's lifetime, the number can be an interesting indicator of the project's sustainability and these are simultaneously clear exploitation evidence!

15.8.3 Accreditation and formal recognition of training

In the context of the project, under the training programs, materials, and certificates that will be prepared, it is important that the partners explore ways to make the training of trainers (as well as of the trainees) more formal, because in that way it can incentivise the joining of future participants to be specialised in using the project results and thus multiplying the implementation cases.

15.8.4 Networking/Lobbying

Influencing high-level change in policy and systems is a real possibility if project managers co-operate effectively and at the right levels. This is essentially a process of networking with all relevant stakeholders, so building contacts and attending meetings is

vital – which is hard work but the only way. The European Commission, European and National Agencies, National Committees and Programme Committees organise events to facilitate such co-operation. Attending events, such as conferences, seminars and debates, provides an ideal opportunity to showcase your results and also leads to fruitful contacts to enhance networking & lobbying. Some projects choose to hold some kind of European dedicated events (seminar, conference, workshop...), preferably in central EU venues, and with the involvement of relevant decision-makers, stakeholders, and funding entities. The events aim to convince the participants to introduce/take into account the products and approach of the project, which might be considered in policy formulation.

15.8.5 Develop New Partnerships

The long-lasting effects of co-funded projects can only be possible through effective partnerships, mostly as soon as the project is reaching its end. At this stage, most of the products are finalised and thus, it is easier to present a tangible resource to the project's stakeholders and show them how that specific product brings them benefits without costs.

15.9 Keep this in mind!

For a successful exploitation:

- The products and information should be in the right place but communicating the usefulness of the products is the key;
- Use the appropriate exploitation mechanisms as described;
- Incentives are important;
- Distribute the products to decision makers, opinion leaders and significant stakeholders;
- The deliverable message needs to fit the needs of the target groups;
- Be proud of the results and “keep the light burning” after the end of the project;
- In order to get better, never be satisfied;
- Create a business plan with further goals. Keep IPR in mind;
- It is important to keep yourself motivated and to network for your project/product even after its end. A very important success factor is the mind-set of the project team;
- Try to expand the target group. There is always the possibility for beneficiaries to become “new starters”;
- Successful exploitation needs to be supported by successful dissemination. The impact of the project needs to be described;
- In general, BlueRev partners should always:
 1. obtain and utilise end-user validation e.g. questionnaire analysis; evidence of effective use of outputs;
 2. maintain products updated, upgraded based on ongoing feedback;

3. keep regular networking and lobbying activities;
4. update website's news constantly;
5. assure appropriate exploitation mechanisms;
6. keep regular contact with the relevant stakeholders;

16 APPENDIX A - Presentation of the identity and concept.

LOBA®

**branding
proposal**

bluerev

01

concept

- concept

keywords

blue economy
ocean
bio-based value chain
climate crisis
community
awareness
guidelines
knowledge

02

solution

BlueRev

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA

BlueRev

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA*

CUSTOMER **EXPERIENCE** DESIGN

LOBA

Bio-based revitalisation
of local communities

Bio-based revitalisation
of local communities

CUSTOMER **EXPERIENCE** DESIGN

LOBA

BlueRev

typography

The typography of the logo was all worked with some wavy details as an association to the water concept. We achieved a lettering with personality, robust but at the same time, sober.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

symbol

The brand symbol brings together various emerging concepts to the project.

The main one is the concept of water as an association to the oceans, to the waves of the sea, which is the element that is basis of the project.

The three lines can be associated with the knowledge layers of the project and, simultaneously, the various actors

involved in it: each of them will be a strong contribution to the project.

The general shape of the symbol looks like a square with rounded corners and this reinforce the idea of core and solution.

The position of the symbol in the upper right corner resembles the position of a flag that refers to navigation and exploration of the ocean.

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Healthy oceans are a
precondition for a thriving
blue economy.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA

LOBA®

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA

BlueRev

Valorization of
blue resources
through sustainable
co-innovation

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.
In posuere commodo lectus non placerat. Aenean risus
turpis, litora in accumsan eget, sodales quis leo.
Mauris sed eros ultricies, finibus nunc et, laeibus ex.
Fusce ullamcorper id metus ut lobortis.

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CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA[®]

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA*

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA*

BlueRev

Bio-based revitalisation
of local communities

Blue color palette

Brand Colors

Minerva Modern

Elegant, formal and and
corporate font.

Use in running text and longer titles.

CUSTOMER **EXPERIENCE** DESIGN

Typography

abcdefghijklmn
opqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

ABCDEFGHIJKLMN
OPQRSTUVWXYZ

LOBA*

niblick

Disruptive source to reinforce
the ocean concept.

Use in very short titles and
large visual dimension.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

Typography

abcdefghijklmn
opqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

ABCDEFGHIJKLMN
OPQRSTUVWXYZ

LOBA*

play

video

think. connect. grow. — **fiercely.**

LOBA[®]

thank you.

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loba.com

talk to us

+351 256 668 413 • geral@loba.pt

oliveira de azeméis

Largo Luís de Camões,
Edifício Rainha, Piso 12
3720-232 Oliveira de Azeméis
Portugal

aveiro

Rua José Afonso 28, loja 3
3800-438 Aveiro
Portugal

guarda

M5 - Business Center
Avenida Rainha Dona
Amélia 74
6300-749 Guarda
Portugal

lisboa

Edifício Oeiras Office
Rua Marechal Teixeira
Rebelo, 2, 1º D
2780-271 Oeiras
Portugal

porto

Via do Castelo do Queijo
395, 4100-429
Porto
Portugal

17 APPENDIX B – Branding manual

**This document was
created to keep the
brand consistency.**

follow the instructions

BlueRev

Healthy oceans are a
precondition for a thriving
blue economy.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA

brand manual
index

5 Logotype

10 Size and Guidelines

13 Colors and Typography

17 Graphics

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA

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BlueRev

Main
version

BlueRev

This is the main version
of the logotype.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA*

BlueRev

Negative
version

BlueRev

This is the negative
version of the logotype.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

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BlueRev

Mono-
chromatic

BlueRev

This is the monochromatic
version of the logotype.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

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BlueRev

Claim
version

This is the claim version
of the logotype.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

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Bio-based revitalisation
of local communities

LOBA*

02.

size and guidelines

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA®

BlueRev

Sizes and margins

Margins of the logotype

Margins of the logotype.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

screen

print

with claim

without claim

LOBA

BlueRev

Sizes and margins

Size of the logotype

Size of the logotype.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA[®]

03.

colors and typography

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA

Blue color palette

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

niblick

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the ocean concept.

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Use in very short titles and
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CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

abcdefghijklmn
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0123456789

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LOBA®

Minerva Modern

Elegant, formal and
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Use in running text and longer titles.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

abcdefghijklmnop
opqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

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OPQRSTUVWXYZ

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BlueRev

graphics

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The three lines can be associated with the knowledge layers of the project and the various actors involved in it.

The general shape of the symbol looks like a square with rounded corners and this reinforce the idea of core and solution.

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download

all the logo versions [here](#)

18 APPENDIX C – Power Point Presentation

Key Elements

Funding Scheme

CSA – Coordination and Support Action

Budget

€ 2 222 952,50

Duration

3 years (1st September 2022
– 31st August 2025)

BlueRev Consortium

Coordinator

APRE

Agenda per la Promozione
della Ricerca Europea

Partners

Food & Bio Cluster
Denmark

Pilot Region

DISTRETTO DELLA PESCA
E CRESCITA BLU

Pilot Region

LOBA®

Partners

UiA University
of Agder

Eesti Maaülikool
Estonian University of Life Sciences

Pilot Region

NIBIO
NORWEGIAN INSTITUTE OF
BIOECONOMY RESEARCH

Funded by
the European Union

*BlueRev Pilot Regions

BlueRev Main Objective

BlueRev aims to select a range of systems in the blue bio-based sector in **3 different pilot regions** (Denmark, Italy and Estonia), to **tailor value chains**, from valorization of co-products as feedstock to processing/conversion to final products, in order to **revitalize local communities**, both in a territorial and social sense.

BlueRev Specific Objectives

SO1

To engage local communities of stakeholders to analyse social and economic barriers and potentialities, to improve awareness of stakeholders and to improve communication between them about opportunities for collaboration along the bio-based value chain (WP2-5)

SO3

To assess existing/develop new monitoring systems and indicators of the effectiveness of existing governance schemes, to analyse pilot regions and to allow replication across the EU (WP3-6)

SO2

To analyse social and economic barriers and potentialities in pilot regions to enable the transition towards socially and environmentally responsible behaviour through new informed governance and especially social innovation developed within the project (WP3-WP4)

SO4

To analyse and develop new or updated business models and local capacities and innovation actors to enable sufficient impacts and performances of the whole pilot regions value chains (WP3-WP4)

BlueRev Specific Objectives

SO5

Environmental footprint of the whole value chains of pilot regions, through LCA analysis (WP3)

SO6

To carry out a training programme to increase skilled jobs opportunities and small-scale establishments in the bio-based sector and to support the development of communication of innovation for small businesses and for business-to-consumers (WP5)

SO7

To reach a sound impact of performed activities by involving all the stakeholders through a wide dissemination and awareness campaign (WP6)

BlueRev Concept and Methodology

- Analysis of social innovation process
- Analysis of business models
- Analysis of the governance models
- Environmental assessment

- Repository of existing practices
- Alternative solutions
- Indicators

- Engagement of stakeholders in co-creation of nem solutions

- Engagement of stakeholders in co-creation of nem solutions
- Stakeholders Board Local actors (Pilot Regions)
- Workshops, web-based platform

- Case studies demonstration
Training/Coaching programme

- 3 Local workshops to transfer new solutions to all stakeholders
- 2 Best practices guidelines for small businesses

- Communication and Dissemination
- Replication throughout Europe

BlueRev Pilot Regions

Partner	Region	Value chain	Stakeholders	Description
<p>Use of fish side-streams for nutraceutical, food and feed applications.</p>	<p>300+ members, including Companies producing high value-added products from improved utilisation of side streams (e.g. Royal Greenland, Jeka Fish). Local authorities: Lemvig Kommune (The municipal of Lemvig); Naalakkersuisut (Government of Greenland).</p>	<p>The uptake of blue bio-based economy value chains faces problems related to lack of skilled personnel Logistic infrastructures Being an outermost region (Greenland)</p>		

BlueRev Pilot Regions

Partner	Region	Value chain	Stakeholders	Description
 Use of red algae biomass for food nutraceuticals and cosmetic industry.	Stakeholders' network of 170+ stakeholders, including Companies and laboratories (e.g. Vetik Ltd.,) developing formulations for factories and manufacturers and a final mixture consisting of different substances (texturising agents, emulsifiers, etc.); research and development organisations (e.g. Estonian University of Life Sciences, Tallinn University of Technology); Local authorities (Saare municipality).	A transition from traditional technologies for processing red algae to modern technologies in order to extract substances that could be valuable inputs for other industries. To expand the scope of blue bioeconomy in the region based on others local aquatic resources, not only red algae (by taking advantage of the experiences gained in the others pilot regions). The main bottlenecks include: -Lack of skilled R&D specialists in the company and region. -Gap in the connection between production and end-users in new industries.		

BlueRev Pilot Regions

Partner	Region	Value chain	Stakeholders	Description
<p>Marine bioactive compounds and ingredients from fish processing residuals and algae for industrial applications (e.g. cosmetics nutraceuticals)</p>	<p>DFBG includes 134 enterprises and 46 institutions, associations, universities, Research and culture centres, among which companies producing fish by-products (e.g. Blue ocean), RTOS (University of Palermo, Research centre CNR-IAS, University consortium province of and local stakeholders (Department of Mediterranean fisheries of the Sicily region, Confindustria Trapani).</p>	<p>The main bottlenecks are represented by the lack of infrastructures and governance measures/business models for collection, stocking and selling marine by-products and by the gap in the connection between production and end-users (e.g. companies in the sector of cosmetics, nutraceuticals and pharmaceuticals).</p>		

Overview of challenges in Pilot Regions

01

The lack of logistic infrastructures and governance measures/business models for collection, stocking and selling of marine by-products

02

A gap in the connection between production and end-users

03

Lack of skilled personnel and R&D specialists in the company and region

04

Being an outermost region (specifically, Greenland)

05

A transition from traditional technologies to modern technologies

BlueRev Expected Results

Engagement of at least 500 stakeholders and 3 pilot regions (WP2)

1 Analysis (business models, governance structure and social measures) of the 3 pilot regions under study within the project (WP3)

Programme of at least 6 workshops in WP3 (3) and 4 (3) (at least 10 participants per each workshop) aiming at helping local stakeholders to analyse social and economic barriers and potentialities in their regions to enable the transition towards socially and environmentally responsible behaviour through new business models, informed governance and especially social innovation developed within the project

At least 2 new models to identify or set-up social innovations to enable stakeholders to switch to socially and environmentally responsible behaviour and to advance the role of 'social enterprise' model for local communities (D4.1); 1 New business model (D4.2). 1 New governance model (D4.3).

BlueRev Expected Results

1 best practices guideline (WP4) and at least 3 demonstration workshops for the 3 pilot regions under study within the project, ~50-100 participants per workshop (WP5).

A training programme that focuses on helping local stakeholders to develop skilled jobs and small-scale establishments in the bioeconomy: 4 modules for a total of 13 lessons for association of producers, master and PhD students, 100-200 participants in total. (WP5).

1 best Practice guideline supporting the development of communication of innovation for small businesses and for business-to-consumers (WP5).

At least 10,000 recipients of dissemination campaign (numbers of stakeholders and activities targeted are reported in section 2.2-2.3) (WP6).

BlueRev Workplan

thank you

BlueRev

Bio-based revitalisation
of local communities

Consortium

Food & Bio Cluster
Denmark

LOBA®

Eesti Maaülikool
Estonian University of Life Sciences

NIBIO
NORWEGIAN INSTITUTE OF
BIOECONOMY RESEARCH

@BlueRevEU bluerevproject.eu info@bluerevproject.eu

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19 APPENDIX D – Backgrounds of the basic templates

Contact us

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 @BlueRevEU

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20 APPENDIX E – Supporting materials

20.1 Badges

Name

Organisation

Funded by
the European Union

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the European Union

BlueRev

Bio-based revitalisation
of local communities

Name

Organisation

Funded by
the European Union

20.2 Letterhead paper

20.3 Background for teleconferences

www.blurevproject.eu

www.blurevproject.eu

20.4 Email signature

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Project Manager

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info@bluerevproject.eu

 @BlueRevEU

20.5 Folder

20.6 Business Card

Raquel Nogueira

Project Manager
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bluerevproject.eu
info@bluerevproject.eu

 @BlueRevEU

20.7 Template email

Email Title

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Etiam elit magna, viverra sit amet quam vitae, ullamcorper facilisis elit. Aenean pretium id nibh vel interdum. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Etiam elit magna, viverra sit amet quam vitae, ullamcorper facilisis elit. Aenean pretium id nibh vel interdum. Pellentesque habitant morbi tristique senectus et netus et malesuada fames ac turpis egestas. Duis urna quam, dapibus ac leo in, varius rutrum justo. Morbi sed pharetra massa. Sed vel porttitor lectus. Nullam pharetra leo at dolor posuere efficitur. Aliquam tempus quis dolor sed feugiat. Praesent in metus vitae velit gravida vulputate. Donec non consectetur tellus. Proin libero nulla, efficitur eu gravida id, vulputate non sem. Ut semper ex urna, iaculis condimentum.

Subtitle if needed

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- > Integer at dui vel lectus aliquam tempus sollicitudin in tortor.
- > Quisque consectetur ante eget aliquet sagittis.
- > Pellentesque et mi interdum lectus gravida volutpat sed id odio.

Best Regards,
BlueRev Project

bluerevproject.eu

[f](#) [in](#) [t](#) [@](#) [@BlueRevEU](#)

consortium

21 APPENDIX F – Graphics kit overview

LOBA

graphics kit

bluerev

LOBA

project concept

graphics kit

LOBA[®]

project structure

graphics kit

LOBA[®]

target groups ecosystem

graphics kit

National, regional, local authorities
and regional clusters

Primary biomass producers,
associations and cooperatives

Organisations and SMEs

Civil society organisations,
including NGOs

Knowledge providers and
scientific communities

Marginalised groups

LOBA[®]

geographical coverage

graphics kit

LOBA[®]

project main goals

graphics kit

Awareness

Innovation

BlueRev Symbol

Revitalization

Entrepreneurship

Local Communities

Bio-based revitalisation
of local communities

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